

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

**Document ID: D5.15 Material for Awareness, Communication,
Dissemination and Outreach no2**

04/07/2022

RAMONES funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET Proactive programme via grant agreement No.101017808

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	RAMONES		
Name	Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems		
Start Date	1 Jan 2021	End Date	31 Dec 2024
Program	H2020-EU.1.2.2. - FET Proactive		
Call ID	H2020-FETPROACT-2020-2	Topic	FETPROACT-EIC-08-2020 - Environmental Intelligence
Grant No	101017808	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Document Id	D5.15		
Document Title	Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2		
Due Date	30-Jun-2022	Delivery Date	4-Jul-2022
Lead Beneficiary	NKUA(1)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA(1), IST-ID(2), EVOL(3), ENS(4), NTUA(5), PLOA(6), UDUR(7), UCA(8)		
Editor(s)	Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA)		
Authors (s)	Eleni Petra, Effie Zafirakopoulou, Stavroula Kazana, Konstantina Bejelou, Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA), Antonio Pascoal, Pedro Batista, Luis Sebastiao (IST-ID), Konstantin Kebkal (EVOL), Javier Escartin (ENS), Konstantinos Karantzalos, Valsamis Ntouskos (NTUA), Angelos Mallios (PLOA), Konstantinos Nikolopoulos (UDUR), Lydia Maigne (UCA)		
Contributor (s)			
Reviewer(s)	Angelos Mallios (PLOA)		
Workpackages	WP5 - Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities		
Version	V2.0	Stage	Re-submitted
Distribution	Public		
Keywords	Pathfinder, EIC, FET, Radioactivity, Environmental Intelligence, Underwater Research	Type	Websites, patents filling, etc.

Document Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1.0	04.07.2022	Document version submitted to EC	Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA)	--
2.0	14.11.2022	Document version re-submitted to EC	Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA)	

Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling needs and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

This document has been produced through funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the RAMONES project Consortium and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole, nor the individual partners

that have implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 27 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FET	Future and Emerging Technologies
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
SoA	State of the Art
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1. Introduction to Dissemination, Outreach and Communication Materials	9
1.1 Context	9
1.2 Structure of the document	9
1.3 General Objectives and approach	10
2. Material's target group/audience	12
3. New material for the website - Final release	13
4. New dissemination material	16
5. Conclusion	23

Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modelling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth and human health. RAMONES will provide tools for long-term, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, propose new AI-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these can be achieved by combining SoA equipment from various disciplines in well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. Additionally, one of the main goals is to introduce novel ways of monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals from medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies.

An additional key task of the project is to increase local citizens, as well as stakeholders and policymakers' awareness and involvement based on diverse dissemination, communication, and outreach activities, through scientific evidence and FAIR data principles. RAMONES is adopting several intense dissemination and communication strategies towards raising public awareness and attracting citizen involvement through multiple identified channels and target groups.

The main aim of this deliverable is to provide the details of various branding documentation to achieve the "Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation" goals. The deliverable is relevant to the previous deliverables: D.5.14 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1 of M8 and D5.10 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no1 of M12. The main scope of this deliverable is the introduction of additional branding documentation concerning webinars, seminars and educational purposes. We persistently aim to clearly define a RAMONES branding scheme and

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2

disseminate the project's objectives by investing on visual promotion of the project's logo, website, social media, but also retain the association of people using the materials with the project.

1. Introduction to Dissemination, Outreach and Communication Materials

1.1 Context

This document is part of Work Package 5 (WP5, *Citizen Awareness, Communication and Dissemination Activities*), and in particular of Task T5.3 on Raising Citizens Awareness, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities.

The document continues to outline the vision, strategy and a specific plan of opportunities offered to expand the baseline dissemination of the RAMONES project via related documentation. The document builds upon the Deliverable D5.14 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1 (M8), reporting on the updates, extensions, improvements and upgrades of existing dissemination, outreach and communication materials, providing information and details on new materials for the same goals, as well as presenting the final version of the RAMONES official website.

The RAMONES dissemination, outreach and communication plan extends the roadmap to maximize the output from the project effort in the direction of:

- (i) bringing its results to the wider and most appropriate audience that will be interested or motivated in exploiting or uptaking it, and
- (ii) create a minimal, but effective, visual representation of the project and communicate it to stakeholders and the public.

According to the EU definition, outreach activities are expected to engage a large audience. Our general goal is to promote the research project, raise public and industry interest and maximize the dissemination impact via various communication channels. At the same time, RAMONES brand name can be founded, strengthened and grown. In line with the above, designing, creating and sharing RAMONES material is expected to serve these goals.

1.2 Structure of the document

The current document is organized as follows:

1. **Objectives and approach:** Consolidate the objectives to raise awareness, communication, dissemination and outreach and the relevant approaches for consequent development as reported in Deliverable D5.14

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2

2. **Material's target group/audience.** The dissemination material is distributed to various target audiences (in research, business, technology and education) during various events defined in the corresponding section of the document.
3. **Dissemination Material.** Finally, the updated and the new material created for further dissemination is described in some detail.

1.3 General Objectives and approach

The general objectives of the RAMONES citizen awareness, communication, dissemination and outreach and how they will be implemented are also presented here (see D5.14)

Table 1. Communication, Dissemination, Citizen Awareness, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation Plan approach.

Type of Activity	RAMONES Objectives	Means and Activities
Communication	1. Increase RAMONES visibility in terms of activities and outcomes; receive valuable feedback	Communication effort aiming at the targeted multiple audience beyond RAMONES community; Exploit feedback strengthening potentials and exploitation
	2. Inform Society and communities / enhance the engagement with stakeholders	Communicate project outcomes to a broad, diverse audience. Targeted communication efforts towards target groups (radioactivity, environmental, marine robotics, social scientists, analysts) and relevant stakeholders.
Dissemination	3. Position RAMONES as a top-rank EIC project and in Environmental Intelligence European projects ecosystem	Intensive dissemination activities are linked to the offered project outcomes to promote them during their operational phase within the considered sectors and the Environmental Intelligence community.
	4. Boost networking and engagement strategy of the RAMONES results	Targeted and synchronized dissemination, communication, exploitation and communities' engagement activities aimed at all target audiences and policymakers.
Raise Awareness	5. Share knowledge of the offered methodologies and instrumentation	Project development along with communication and dissemination activities and targeted communities' engagement aiming at primary target audiences.

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2

	6. Raise awareness and demonstrate how RAMONES outcomes (methodologies and instrumentation) can cater to the needs of the stakeholders and the communities	Communication efforts along with carefully designed activities for maximizing impact including hands-on training of several primary targeted audiences.
Outreach	7. Engage large audiences and bring knowledge and expertise from RAMONES objectives and outcomes to the relevant communities, policy makers and stakeholders, as well as the general public.	Outreach activities will be accomplished via approaches specialized to audiences in question, such as workshops, conferences, webinars, datathons/hackathons always with the appropriate communication material

In particular, the main objectives are:

- to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work.
- to maximize the impactful visibility of the project's work and achievements.
- to engage stakeholders that can support project sustainability through both update and feedback and can further empower the vision around EIC and Environmental Intelligence goals.
- to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to third parties focusing especially on the H2020 and Environmental Intelligence landscape.

Our approach remains solid and can be summarized under the following conditions:

- **Announce RAMONES to the scientific community:** actions are required to properly explain the RAMONES's vision and strategy, identify key target groups (targeted interest groups in research, business and technology) and define contents and channels for each target.
- **Partners: the first believers, first users and first promoters.** It is necessary to gain the engagement of the partners (by means of internal communication) and to take advantage of each partner's knowledge and contacts to boost their best contributions. A recurrent task of enhancing and sharing synergies will drive the best achievements.
- **Understand the real needs of the target groups (Research groups, RIs stakeholders, scientific groups, technology providers, policy makers/stakeholders, general public):**

to achieve a deep understanding of real needs it is necessary to enable and promote 2-way communication channels.

- **Tune the offer:** to define values, services and solutions, we need to transfer to the communities, stakeholders and wide public the identified needs.
- **Boost the demand:** By means of close access to research, public communities and stakeholder needs, identification of the communication messages, and dissemination of content and benefits of RAMONES outcomes
- **Knowledge hub:** Content and knowledge repository implies coordination of any news and contents among project partners, and their later dissemination and storage.
- **Measurement & Control:** No achievement can be made without its measurement and control, both for reporting purposes and for best possible results tactics in order to strengthen the recurrent collaboration among all the partners.

2. Material's target group/audience

Based on the RAMONES progress in dissemination so far, we focus on the same target audience groups defined in the prior deliverable concerning communication and dissemination material (D5.14). We identify these target groups as:

- researchers
- funders
- industry parties
- policy makers
- stakeholders
- general public including journalists, students, scientists, innovators, startups, NGOs, or the society in a broader sense.

The dissemination material will be also shared within all the project partners.

The main events in which these materials will be distributed to the above-mentioned audiences are webinars, seminars and events of educational purposes, such as summer schools and training events. Thus, the material aims to consolidate the RAMONES brand and disseminate the project's activities.

3. New material for the website - Final release

This section presents and displays the final release of the RAMONES website. The whole structure and the developed pages have already been presented in detail in the deliverable D5.23.

A new option has been added in the top menu of the header in order for the submitted deliverables of the project to be available and accessible for the public. Every title of the available deliverables can be selected and a corresponding pdf opens in a new page.

In Figures 1 & 2, the structure of the Top head menu and the Main menu of the header with the new option, as well as the content of this section are depicted:

Figure 1. Website, detail of the Top head and Main menu section

- **D1.2 1st instrument release and laboratory testing report**
- **D2.1 Preliminary report on Positioning, Cooperative Control and Navigation**
- **D5.1 Repository, Information System and Risk no1**
- **D5.9 Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement & Exploitation Plan**
- **D5.10 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no1**

Figure 2. Website, the Deliverables section and its content

In addition, the background of the Environmental Intelligence section was changed after the acquisition of the Slocum glider from IST-ID.

Figure 3. Website, the Environmental Intelligence section and its content

Moreover, the News, Events and Publications sections are constantly being updated with the latest activities of the consortium, such as participation in meetings, conferences, workshops and other events, webinars, collaborations, talks, relevant papers etc., as presented in the following Figures.

Important new features of the website that enhance the maximum dissemination of news, events and major achievements of the project in a synchronised fashion is the installation and activation of special plug-ins which facilitate automatic posting to all major social media accounts of the project. In addition, plugins that increase the SEO ranking of the website in popular search engines (e.g google) have been installed and optimized, while including multiple keywords relevant to the project concept and output.

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2

Figure 4. Website, detail of News section

Figure 5. Website, Events section details

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2

Figure 6. Website, Publications section details

4. New dissemination material

The project team has already created hardcopy material, gadgets and various documents incorporating the brand image, the color palette and the identified style of RAMONES, in order to achieve the project communication objectives, strengthen project's identification, consolidate engagement and arouse the interest of the project among a varied public. The aforementioned dissemination material was described in detail in the D.5.14 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no1 of M8 and D5.10 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no1 of M12.

Figure 7. The RAMONES logos that were designed at the beginning of the project.

Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2

In addition to the above-mentioned material, further branding documentation was designed to supplement the early material and meet the special needs of the project concerning webinars, seminars and educational purposes. The designed material is in accordance with the particular brand image style of the project (unique color palette and typography).

The dissemination material comprises the following:

- webinar template background
- seminar template announcement
- activities template announcement

Some examples of the branding documentation are shown in the following Figures:

Figure 8. RAMONES Template for presentations.

Figure 9. An example of how the presentation template in Fig. 2 has been employed in a recent project presentation during a webinar.

Figure 10. An example of a RAMONES banner template for webinars.

The template in Figure 10 reflects on our general approach for communicating and disseminating RAMONES activities and events in various channels and different artifacts, such as social media posts, registration forms, email and hard copy invitations, and more. An example of how Figure 10 can be used in such a way is illustrated in Figure 11, where the banner template has been adopted for the announcement of the webinar “Hunting Radioactivity in the Depths of the Ocean” on 28 June 2022.

Figure 11. An example of a RAMONES template for webinars.

Figure 12. More RAMONES template designs for webinars.

Other events that the aforementioned templates were used:

- 85th Thessaloniki International Fair, Thessaloniki, Greece, 11-19 September 2021

- RAMONES First International Workshop & Technical Meeting, Athens, Greece, 9-10 November 2021
- FRAGRANCE Workshop, NKUA - Athens, Greece, 24 June 2022

- 7as Jornadas de Engenharia Hidrográfica conference, held at the Instituto Hidrográfico, Lisbon, Portugal, 21-23 June 2022

All templates have the RAMONES logo in blue background or in a background depicting the ocean seafloor or some variations of it. Also, the color bar is displayed jointly with graphic

circles of various sizes. Additionally, the text of every document is relevant to the subject of the corresponding event.

The material was designed in high resolution, not only for digital use, but also for printing in good quality. This material can be distributed and promoted in any related event organized by the RAMONES project team to maximize the impact of dissemination to various audiences. The content of the documents is relevant to RAMONES goals, services and benefits.

All dissemination materials are available on the project's common Cloud drive and are offered for the consortium's use.

5. Conclusion

With the present Deliverable, we highlight the promotion of the RAMONES brand and the related documentation, as well as the final release of the project's website. A range of various types of promotional material concerning templates for webinars, seminars and educational activities were designed to support the dissemination and outreach objectives of the project. The branding and style of RAMONES documentation supports the vision of the project for communicating the scope and objectives to a wide audience including researchers, industry parties, stakeholders and the general public and is further consolidated in this deliverable with new material.